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Multi-parameter Ocean-atmosphere Interactions in the Indian Ocean Around the Western Sri Lankan Region from 2002-2025

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Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of multi-parameter ocean-atmosphere interactions in the Western Indian Ocean around Sri Lanka (78.75°E-80°E, 5.5°N-10°N) using 23 years of satellite-derived and reanalysis data (2002-2025). The relationships between sea surface temperature (SST), chlorophyll a concentration, precipitation, heat fluxes, and atmospheric dynamics to understand climate variability and marine ecosystem responses in this coastal region were examined. The analysis revealed significant inverse correlations between SST and biological productivity, with chlorophyll a concentrations showing strong negative relationships to temperature variations ($r=-0.742$, $p<0.001$). This correlation strength is notably higher than reported values from the Bay of Bengal ($r=-0.35$ to -0.55), suggesting that thermal stratification exerts stronger control on productivity in Sri Lankan coastal waters compared to the salinity-dominated Bay of Bengal system. Long-term trends indicate consistent warming of 0.15 °C per decade, exceeding global ocean averages and comparable to the upper range of Arabian Sea warming rates (0.12-0.15 °C per decade), coupled with a modest increase in primary productivity (+0.04 mg m⁻³ per decade). This contrasts with declining productivity trends reported for the central Arabian Sea (-0.03 to -0.08 mgm⁻³ per decade) and stable trends in the Bay of Bengal, suggesting region-specific responses to climate forcing. Strong positive correlations were observed between latent heat flux and precipitation patterns ($r=0.683$), suggesting robust monsoon-driven ocean-atmosphere coupling. Seasonal analysis demonstrated peak chlorophyll a concentrations during the southwest monsoon (June-September, mean: 1.89 mgm⁻³) when cooler temperatures and enhanced nutrient availability promote phytoplankton growth, though the seasonal amplitude (factor of ~2) is substantially lower than the Arabian sea upwelling zones (factor of 3-10). While our statistical models showed reasonable calibration performance ($R^2=0.78$), independent validation revealed reduced predictive skill ($R^2=0.54$), highlighting fundamental limitations of correlation-based approaches. These findings contribute to understanding regional ocean-atmosphere dynamics.

Keywords: ocean-atmosphere interactions; sea surface temperature; chlorophyll; monsoon; climate variability